
Identifying prominent actors in historical networks: The case of the New Education Movement

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Abstract

This study explores the structure and key actors of the British New Education Movement (1905–1935) using two-mode network analysis. It demonstrates how network approaches can deepen historical research by uncovering connections among reformers and organizations, offering new perspectives on leadership, influence, and the role of marginalized groups in shaping the movement.

Research Questions

The research addresses two main questions:

- How did the New Education Movement sustain its influence over time despite ideological diversity?
- What distinct roles did individuals play in the movement, and how did their interactions contribute to its adaptability and goals?

Data and Methodology

The study draws on archival materials, biographical records, and organizational documents to map affiliations between 42 reformers and 31 organizations. A novel approach to reconstructing networks from unstructured historical data enabled the identification of ties among actors and institutions. Two-mode network analysis preserved the duality of people and organizations, enabling the study of both individual roles and broader movement dynamics.

This methodology bridges quantitative and qualitative methods, using historical sources to validate network patterns and contextualize findings. Amid growing interest in using network analysis in historical studies, this study provides new perspectives on whether and how network measures have correspondence to historical reality (e.g., Düring 2016).

Unlike previous studies relying on pre-existing datasets, this approach facilitates research on contexts where archival material is fragmented or incomplete. The integration of documentary evidence ensures that the analysis captures both structural insights and nuanced historical realities.

Key Findings

The study identifies two complementary roles that sustained the movement:

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- **Conveners** fostered tightly-knit groups focused on specialized reforms, such as early childhood education or progressive pedagogy.
- **Mediators** bridged disparate groups, fostering connections across ideological and institutional boundaries and enabling coordinated action at the national level.

The movement's network was densely interconnected, with overlapping memberships that facilitated collaboration and adaptability. This structure allowed the movement to address emerging societal and political challenges during the early 20th century, achieving key goals such as expanding access to education and introducing progressive teaching methods.

While the movement's leadership was male-dominated, the analysis highlights the significant contributions of women. Reformers such as Beatrice Ensor and Alice Woods played pivotal roles in connecting organizations, driving institutional change, and promoting educational equality. This finding demonstrates the method's capacity to highlight the contributions of historically underrepresented groups, offering a corrective to traditional historiographies that often marginalize their roles.

Methodological Contributions

This study advances the application of network analysis in historical research, showcasing its ability to bridge the gap between traditional qualitative approaches and computational methods. By reconstructing networks from archival sources, it demonstrates the feasibility of studying social movements without relying on pre-collected datasets, enabling historians to uncover connections in less-documented contexts.

The use of two-mode analysis preserves the complexity of relationships between individuals and organizations, avoiding the oversimplifications inherent in projecting data into single-mode networks. This approach aligns with recent developments in the digital humanities and offers a replicable model for studying other historical movements.

Complementing Previous Research

The findings build on theoretical frameworks proposed by Cunningham (2001) and Diani (2003), who emphasized the importance of horizontal and vertical networks in social movements. While earlier studies on the New Education relied primarily on qualitative evidence, this research provides empirical validation, revealing how conveners and mediators collectively sustained the movement.

Additionally, the study complements historiographical critiques that highlight the male-centric narratives of educational reform. By focusing on networks rather than individual achievements, it brings to light the roles of women and other less privileged groups, who often acted as catalysts for change despite limited formal recognition.

Wider Implications

The study demonstrates how decentralized leadership structures and overlapping affiliations can sustain a social movement over time. The complementary roles of conveners and mediators ensured both grassroots engagement and institutional reform, illustrating how movements can adapt to diverse challenges while achieving systemic impact.

These findings have broader implications for understanding historical social movements, highlighting the importance of distributed leadership and the interplay between local and national actors. The methodological approach also underscores the value of integrating qualitative and quantitative analyses to uncover the dynamics of collective action.

Conclusion

This research enriches our understanding of the New Education Movement by uncovering the interplay between conveners and mediators in sustaining its influence. Its methodological

contributions highlight the potential of network analysis to address gaps in traditional historiography, particularly by illuminating the contributions of underrepresented groups. By bridging qualitative and quantitative methods, the study provides a model for investigating complex historical networks and offers a fresh perspective on the dynamics of leadership and collaboration in social movements.

References

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